

A New Method of Estimating Arsenic in Organo-arsenic Derivatives. Part II.

BY HIRENDRA NATH DAS-GUPTA.

The present communication is a continuation of the work done by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 95), on the problem of estimating arsenic accurately and rapidly in organo-arsenic compounds. There was, however, the limitation that the compounds concerned should contain arsenic in the penta-valent state. The present paper deals with those derivatives in which the metalloid is in the tri-valent state.

Organo-arsenic compounds containing tri-valent arsenic do not liberate iodine from potassium iodide in hydrochloric acid solution and hence the previous method (*loc. cit.*) could not be followed. A careful study of the properties of organo-arsenic derivatives, in which the element is present in the tri-valent state, clearly reveals the fact that most of the compounds are unstable and readily undergo oxidation either simply by atmospheric influence or when treated with simple oxidising agents and are thus converted into corresponding arsinic acids. Advantage was taken of this particular phenomenon, as the acid thus produced readily liberates an equivalent amount of iodine from potassium iodide in hydrochloric acid solution. Hydrogen peroxide was used throughout the experiments as the common oxidising agent. In some cases simple treatment with hydrogen peroxide in the cold was sufficient to bring about the complete oxidation of the compound, whilst in others the peroxide mixture required to be heated for the attainment of the desired result. It was found rather difficult to destroy the excess of the peroxide left after the reaction, by heating either on water-bath or by direct flame and hence to obviate this difficulty, the hot solution, previous to its treatment with acid mixture, was treated with potassium iodide whereby the excess of the peroxide liberated the equivalent amount of iodine. The iodine thus liberated was subsequently treated with *N/10*-sodium thiosulphate solution till the last trace of iodine was removed. This treatment does not interfere with the subsequent steps as the metalloid in the penta-valent state liberates iodine only in acid solution.

After the complete oxidation of the product the same procedure was followed as described in part I (*loc. cit.*).

Compounds selected for analyses belong to different types containing different groupings in the nucleus. The compounds of the arsazine series in which arsenic is in the ring *e.g.*, phenarsazine chloride (Burton and Gibson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, pp. 451, 467, 469); phenarsazine acetate (Burton and Gibson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2277); phenarsazine oxide (Burton and Gibson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, p. 462) and phenarsazine methyl ether, have been analysed and found to give good results. The method is very simple and requires only a small quantity of the substance (10-20 mg.) for analysis. The method of arsenic estimation devised by Norton and Koch (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 27, 1247) failed in the cases of quinoline compounds containing arsenic, but no such difficulty was encountered by adopting this method.

The following table summarises the experimental results of the present investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Substance.	Quantity taken.	$\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ 1'002-N/20.	Arsenic content.	
			Found.	Calc.
Phenylarsenious chloride	0'0140 g.	5 c.c.	33'55	33'5 p.c.
	0'0168	6	33'54	
Phenylarsenious oxide	0'0301	9'55	44'63	44'6
	0'0195	9'35	44'56	
Arsenobenzene	0'0213	11'20	49'29	49'3
	0'0154	8'10	49'30	
	0'0213	11'20	49'29	
	0'0254	13'35	49'30	
Neosalvarsan	0'0273	9'55	32'20	32'1
	0'0242	8'30	32'20	
10-Chloro-5 :10-dihydrophenarsazine	0'0171	4'90	26'91	27'02
	0'0213	6'10	26'90	
10 :10'-Oxy-5 :10-dihydrophenarsazine	0'0137	4'40	30'10	30'00
	0'0145	4'65	30'10	
Phenarsazine-methyl ether.	0'0158	4'60	27'35	27'47
	0'0162	4'70	27'31	
10-Chloro-5-acetyl-5 :10-dihydrophenarsazine	0'0192	4'30	23'4	23'47
	0'0224	5'60	23'4	

Procedure.—The finely powdered substance (10-20 mg.) was taken in

a 300 c.c. conical flask and was covered with 10 c.c. of hydrogen peroxide (12 vol.). The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 15 minutes in order to effect complete oxidation of the substance as seen by its gradual dissolution in excess of the peroxide with change in coloration. In case heating on water-bath did not bring about complete oxidation, the flask was heated over an asbestos board by a low flame after supporting a funnel on the mouth of the flask. The funnel was subsequently washed with distilled water and the washings allowed to run into the main bulk. The oxidised solution was next cooled to the room temperature and then treated with excess of potassium iodide. The unreacted peroxide present at once liberated the equivalent amount of iodine with rise in temperature and the solution assumed a deep brown coloration. The iodine thus set free was gradually treated with *N*/10-sodium thiosulphate solution. Towards the end 2 c.c. of 1 per cent. solution of starch were added and the addition of thiosulphate solution continued till the blue coloration due to free iodine with starch faded away. Owing to the fact that solution of certain organic derivatives are coloured brown, one is apt to be misled by not being able to ascertain whether the existing brown colour is due to free iodine or due to the compound itself; it is therefore advisable to add the starch solution at an earlier stage. (In case the tri-valent derivative under analysis contain a halogen linked to arsenic, the following additional treatment is necessary as the oxidation of such chloro compound gives the corresponding amount of hydrochloric acid. To the oxidised product 2 drops of methyl orange added and then treated drop by drop with *N*/10-sodium carbonate solution till the pink colour changed to yellow. After this the addition of potassium iodide was made as given above). The walls of the flask were then washed carefully with water and the solution cooled. To this glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) and hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.19, 15 c.c.) were added. The solution immediately assumed a blue coloration due to the liberation of iodine from excess of potassium iodide by the metalloid in acid medium with rise in temperature. The solution was therefore, cooled at first and 2 g. more of potassium iodide were added and the liberated iodine was titrated against *N*/20-sodium thiosulphate. As before, the point at which the blue colour just disappears is not the true end point and the addition of the thiosulphate solution should be continued till there is no change in coloration. This is best ascertained by allowing a drop of the standard thiosulphate solution to fall on the solution

and observing whether there is any change in the region in which the drop is allowed to fall. From the amount of the sodium thiosulphate solution required the percentage of the arsenic is calculated from the following relation :

1 C.c. of $N/20$ -thiosulphate $\equiv 0.0009375$ g. of arsenic.

Summary.

Uptil now there is no satisfactory qualitative test for ascertaining the presence of arsenic in a new compound obtained by an attempt to introduce arsenic into the same. The method given may be used as a qualitative test for determining the presence of arsenic.

Nitroarsinic acid derivatives on being reduced by the usual reducing agents might give either an aminoarsinic acid derivative or a nitroarseno derivative. In such doubtful cases the above test is very suitable as the liberation of iodine in acid solution takes place only with the penta-valent derivatives.

Arsenic in quinoline compounds is best determined by this method.

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DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA.

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